

INSURANCE COMPANIES' FINANCIAL STABILITY IMPROVEMENT THROUGH INVESTMENT ACTIVITIES AND ASSET ALLOCATION MECHANISMS IN THEIR OPERATIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18472006>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 29st January 2026

Accepted: 30th January 2026

Online: 31th January 2026

KEYWORDS

insurance companies, financial stability, investment activity, asset allocation, risk management, solvency, liquidity

ABSTRACT

This thesis analyzes the importance of investment activities and asset allocation mechanisms in improving the financial stability of insurance companies. In modern financial markets, insurance companies must ensure solvency, liquidity, and sustainable development under conditions of increasing financial risk. Effective investment management plays a key role in generating stable income and supporting insurers' financial resilience. The study focuses on the relationship between investment portfolio structure, asset diversification, and financial stability indicators. Financial and comparative analysis methods are used to assess how efficient asset allocation contributes to risk reduction and capital adequacy. The findings show that diversified investment strategies and well-managed asset placement significantly enhance the financial stability of insurance companies. The results of this research may serve as a practical basis for improving investment policies and strengthening financial stability in the insurance sector.

Main Part

Investment activity and rational asset allocation mechanisms play a significant role in ensuring the financial stability of insurance companies. Insurance premiums collected and insurance reserves formed by insurers are directed to financial markets as temporarily free funds and contribute to improving the company's financial performance through investment income. Asset allocation mechanisms should be structured based on the principles of liquidity, profitability, and safety. This mechanism предусматривает the formation of an investment portfolio that corresponds to the maturity and volume of the insurance company's liabilities, as well as ensuring asset-liability management (ALM) balance. As a result, the ability to make insurance payments on time increases, and the level of solvency is strengthened.

In addition, a diversified investment policy helps reduce financial risks, limit the negative impact of market fluctuations, and ensure the long-term financial stability of insurance companies. Compliance with prudential regulations and investment limits established by the state guarantees the safety of insurance companies' assets and their stable operation. Thus, the effective organization of investment and asset allocation mechanisms in insurance companies

is one of the key instruments for ensuring financial stability and creates a foundation for the stable and balanced development of the insurance market.

At the end of 2024, insurers' investment portfolios increased by 6.4 percent, reaching UZS 6.54 trillion. The largest share of investments was allocated to bank deposits, which increased by 13.5 percent in 2024 to UZS 4.58 trillion. According to the results of 2024, investments in securities amounted to UZS 1,303.76 billion, accounting for 19.9 percent of total investments of insurance organizations, while other investment directions were also present.

The investment structure of insurance organizations is illustrated in Figure 2.1.1. A comparison of investment indicators for the first nine months of 2024 and 2025 shows significant structural changes in insurance companies' portfolios. While deposits accounted for the largest share of investment assets in 2024 (69%), their share declined to 64% in 2025. This indicates an intensification of investment diversification and the reallocation of capital to other investment directions.

Table 1. Investment Portfolio Structure of Insurance Organizations (2021-2025)

Indicator	2021	2024	2025
Total investment volume (UZS trillion)	3,7	6,5	9,1
Bank deposits (%)	59	70	64
Securities (%)	29		15
Real estate (%)	7-9	7-9	19
Participation in charter capital (%)	4	1-2	1-2

During the period from 2021 to 2025, insurance organizations' investment activities have been characterized not only by quantitative growth but also by significant structural changes. In particular, while the total volume of investments amounted to UZS 3.7 trillion in 2021, it reached UZS 6.5 trillion by 2024, and according to the results of the first nine months of 2025, increased to UZS 9.1 trillion. This indicates a substantial expansion of the investment capacity of insurance organizations.

A structural analysis of the investment portfolio shows that bank deposits remained the leading investment direction throughout the entire period. While the share of deposits accounted for 59 percent in 2021, this indicator increased to 70 percent in 2024. This reflects the priority given by insurance organizations to low-risk and highly liquid assets. The decline in the share of deposits to 64 percent in the first nine months of 2025 indicates a growing emphasis on further diversification of the investment portfolio.

The share of investments allocated to securities shows a consistent downward trend during the analyzed period. Specifically, it decreased from 29 percent in 2021 to 15 percent in the first nine months of 2025. This trend reflects insurance organizations' cautious approach to market risks and their strategy aimed at preserving capital under conditions of instability in the capital market.

Investments in real estate demonstrate notable changes during the period under review. While this investment direction remained relatively stable within the range of 7-9 percent in 2021-2024, its share sharply increased to 19 percent in the first nine months of 2025. This

indicates a significant rise in insurance organizations' interest in real assets, particularly long-term and inflation-resistant investment instruments.

Meanwhile, investments in charter capital participation and other investment directions remained at relatively low levels throughout the period. For instance, participation in charter capital accounted for 4 percent in 2021, while in subsequent years this indicator stabilized at around 1-2 percent. This reflects insurance organizations' cautious investment policy toward high-risk and low-liquidity investment directions.

Overall, the analysis of insurance organizations' investment portfolios shows that during the period 2021-2024, investment policy was mainly characterized by a conservative approach, with a focus on bank deposits and low-risk assets. However, in the first nine months of 2025, a transition toward more balanced diversification of investment portfolios became more pronounced. In particular, the decline in the share of deposits and the significant increase in investments in real estate reflect insurance organizations' strategic decisions aimed at ensuring long-term financial stability and increasing investment returns.

The analysis of insurance organizations' investment portfolios also indicates that during the analyzed period, investment policy was primarily based on the principles of financial stability, liquidity, and risk minimization. At the same time, further diversification of investment portfolios, especially through increasing the share of reliable and high-yield instruments in the securities market, may contribute to strengthening the long-term financial performance of insurance organizations.

This thesis examined the role of investment activities and asset allocation mechanisms in ensuring and improving the financial stability of insurance organizations. The findings indicate that effective investment management and rational asset allocation are among the key determinants of insurers' solvency, liquidity, and long-term financial sustainability. The analysis of investment activities during the period 2021-2025 revealed both quantitative growth and structural changes in insurance organizations' investment portfolios. While investment policy in 2021-2024 was largely conservative, with a strong focus on bank deposits and other low-risk, highly liquid assets, the first nine months of 2025 demonstrated a gradual shift toward more balanced diversification. The declining share of deposits and the increasing allocation to real estate investments reflect strategic efforts by insurance organizations to enhance long-term financial stability and improve investment profitability.

The study also confirmed that adherence to prudential regulations, diversification principles, and asset-liability management (ALM) practices significantly contributes to minimizing financial risks and maintaining capital adequacy. At the same time, the results suggest that further diversification of investment portfolios, particularly through the expansion of reliable and high-yield instruments in the securities market, could strengthen the financial efficiency of insurance organizations in the long term.

Overall, the effective organization of investment activities and asset allocation mechanisms serves as a vital instrument for enhancing the financial stability of insurance organizations and supports the sustainable and balanced development of the insurance market.

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